

SERVICE INNOVATION OF PLATFORM ECOSYSTEMS: A CASE STUDY OF SMART CAMPUS IN CHINA

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The growing demand for more efficient and convenient campus environments has spurred innovation in educational organizations. Many Chinese universities have started building smart campus projects in recent years, aiming to provide users with efficient services. This “smart” has transformed their ways of living. Especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, several offline services were forced to rapidly move online and new technologies were rapidly deployed. It enables universities to continue teaching, learning and operating remotely. Since its emergence as a way to transform the traditional delivery of educational services and related campus activities, smart campuses can be viewed as a service innovation. Smart campuses, with their perceptive, remote, flexible and ubiquitous features that help staff and students work and learn properly, have been the subject of much research attention in recent years. Here the word 'smart' is utilised to explain the intelligence object such as artificial intelligence (AI), cloud computing, and the Internet of things (IoT) that can supply different education services on campuses. So, a smart campus cannot just be seen as an integration of applications and infrastructure around the campus.

Existing literature defines the term ‘smart campus’ from different perspectives. From an educational perspective, a body of literature investigated how a smart campus can support teaching and learning activities. The technical perspective focuses on supporting smart campus operations based on technologies such as the Internet of Things (IoT), cloud computing, artificial intelligence (AI), and a 5G network. Such technologies integrate the services into one platform. The technical view of the smart campus focuses on the platform consisting of various technology components to provide efficient service on different kinds of university activities but overlooks the primary actors of education like students and teachers. However, previous studies on smart campuses have generally taken a technological rather than a socio-technical view, and most of them focus on a specific part of a smart campus, such as a learning platform, and lack a holistic view of a smart campus. In addition, existing research on smart campuses needs to be updated in the context of emerging knowledge, technologies and applications.

This research aims to understand service innovation in public universities and to explore how different actors co-create value in different phases of smart campuses. To further understand service innovation on a platform ecosystem in the context of the public sector in developing countries and to explore its underlying mechanisms. It intends to introduce a service-dominant (S-D) logic to illustrate how the platform ecosystem evolves at different stages in the Chinese smart campus project. The service-dominant platform ecosystem (SDPE) is posited in this research as a term that combines the S-D logic and platform ecosystem theory to deal with the key issues in the smart campus. It can help build a holistic view of service innovation in the platform ecosystem for exploring an existing event and filling in existing gaps within the literature.

To investigate this phenomenon, the authors conducted a case study at a Chinese public university to reveal how this service innovation has evolved regarding smart campuses to support Chinese universities more effectively. Both primary and secondary data were collected in this study. Primary data were gathered through semi-structured interviews and observations, while secondary data were collected through documentary research. The case is divided into four phases to identify its

evolutionary process: the self-renewal phase, the birth phase, the expansion phase and the leadership phase. Different data sources including semi-structured interviews, observations, and documentary studies were collected to obtain a holistic view of the topic. In total, 41 people were interviewed between August and December 2022 and shared their thoughts and experiences. The authors also spent a month conducting participant observation in the study setting between November and December 2022. By doing so, the data is enriched and the data is gathered through semi-structured interviews for validation. 52 key documents including internal documents of the university and third-party companies and official websites of relevant organizations and government authorities were reviewed. A five-phase analysis approach is applied in this study to ensure that the aggregated data can be systematically analyzed.

This research suggests that smart campuses should be user-centric rather than technology-centric. The experience of users and their acceptance play a decisive role in determining the success of smart campus implementation. Second, training to improve the information literacy of teachers and administrators needs to be strengthened. Existing training does not meet the precise and individualized needs of teacher development, and high-quality learning engagement is difficult to sustain effectively. Third, focus on the priority task of data interconnection in smart campuses. Data governance has become an essential requirement for the construction of a university's smart campus. It is difficult to provide quality services without the governance of the various types of human and business data that have formed over the years. Practical implications for practitioners related to campus information technology to promote smart campuses from different perspectives are presented, and recommendations for future research based on the theoretical findings of the case study are provided.

Keywords: Smart campus, Service innovation, Digital platform ecosystem